

INTEGRATION IN THE TURKISH WORLD: FROM A COMMON PAST TO A COMMON FUTURE

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Summary. *This article analyzes the role of Turkic states in the integration processes and the main characteristics of this process. Along with the Turkic states that gained independence after the collapse of the Soviet Union - Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan - the integration of the Turkic states has entered a new stage with the initiative of Turkey. The article examines the possibilities of cooperation in the political, economic, cultural and security fields in the context of the establishment, goals and directions of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS). It also analyzes the main problems facing integration among Turkic states against the background of intra-regional and international political dynamics.*

The main conclusion of the article is that the common historical, linguistic and cultural heritage among Turkic states are the main factors strengthening integration, and the deepening of this unity contributes to regional stability and prospects for mutual development.

Keywords: *security, integration, Turkic-speaking countries, regional cooperation, cultural unity, ethnopolitical, cultural-humanitarian, etc.*

Introduction.

In the era of globalization, regional integration processes have become one of the important directions of international relations. Especially the deepening of cooperation between states that have common language, culture and historical roots creates conditions for this process to take on a natural and sustainable character. Turkic states Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan, which has increased its activity on this platform in recent years are strengthening their integration tendencies among themselves, based on the same ethnopolitical and cultural affiliation. This integration process is developing within the framework of multifaceted cooperation, covering not only cultural-humanitarian areas, but also political, economic and security areas.

The establishment of the Turkic Council (now the Organization of Turkic States) formed the institutional basis for this integration and gave impetus to the systematization of mutual relations among Turkic-speaking countries. This article will analyze the main stages, structural foundations, emerging problems and future prospects of the integration processes taking place among the Turkic states. The goal is to assess the relevance, geopolitical significance and impact of this process on the system of regional and international relations on a scientific basis. In the modern era, regional integration trends are of particular relevance in the system of international relations. The emergence of new forms of interstate cooperation necessitates joint solutions to problems that transcend national borders, and against this background, integration between peoples with a common historical, cultural and linguistic unity is more rapid and sustainable. The Turkic states are a notable example in this regard. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Central Asian and Caucasian republics that gained independence Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan strengthened their cooperation with Turkey in the political, economic and cultural spheres, and as a result, the idea of the unity of the Turkic world began to take on a more realistic content [2]. Although the integration processes among Turkic-speaking states were initially carried out mainly in the humanitarian and cultural fields, over time this cooperation took on an institutional character and the Turkic Council (currently the Organization of Turkic States), established in Nakhchivan in 2009, was an important stage in this direction. Currently, within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States, member

countries are further intensifying their mutual activities in areas such as political dialogue, economic cooperation, energy, transport, security and education.

Against the background of strengthening political, economic and cultural integration between Turkic-speaking states, the role of ethnic groups of Turkic origin and their organizations that do not have the status of an independent state is also growing noticeably. Tatars, Bashkirs, Uyghurs, Chuvash, Sakha, Kazakhs (living in China and Iran), Turkmen and other Turkic peoples living in the Russian Federation, China, Iran and other multinational countries are trying to establish relations with Turkic states through various cultural and national associations and public organizations. These associations, such as the World Uyghur Congress, the Tatar National Cultural Autonomies, the Bashkir People's Congress, and the South Azerbaijan National Movement, serve both to protect Turkicness at the diaspora level and to promote recognition of Turkish identity in the international arena. Through such institutions, Turkic states, on the one hand, expand cultural integration, and on the other hand, support the protection of the rights of Turkic-speaking communities in various regions. This confirms that the Turkic-speaking community is not limited to interstate cooperation, but that non-state actors also perform important functions [12].

The purpose of this article is to analyze the historical foundations, current status and development prospects of integration processes among Turkic states, and to scientifically investigate the challenges and strategic opportunities they face. The topic is of great importance both in terms of regional security and stability and the strengthening of the pan Turkic identity.

Relevance of the topic. In the context of globalization, regional integration processes have become one of the important directions of the system of international relations. [17] These processes develop more naturally, especially between states that share a common language, history, culture and religious values. The deepening of relations between the Turkic states and the formation of strategic partnerships are giving rise to the emergence of new geopolitical orders in the regional and international security architecture of the 21st century. The increase in cooperation between Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan is not limited only to the strengthening of economic and trade relations, but also necessitates the intensification of integration in the political, cultural, transport, energy and security spheres. The Turkic states Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan occupy a special place in this regard. The linguistic and cultural proximity between these states creates a favorable basis for integration and acts as one of the main factors ensuring the sustainability of cooperation [13]. This cooperation took on a formal and institutional character with the establishment of the Turkic Council in Nakhchivan in 2009. In 2021, the organization was renamed the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), and the “Turkic World 2040 Vision” document, adopted at the summit held in Istanbul that year, defined the long-term strategic directions of integration (Turkic Council, 2021). This document encouraged political coordination, economic cooperation, digitalization, energy security, and unity among member countries in the humanitarian fields.

The new geopolitical realities emerging in the region following Azerbaijan's military-political success in Karabakh in 2020 have opened up new opportunities for the Turkic states in terms of building the physical infrastructure of cooperation. In this context, the Zangezur corridor project is of strategic importance not only in terms of restoring Azerbaijan's land connection with Nakhchivan, but also in terms of opening direct transport and trade routes between the Turkic states as a whole [1].

At the same time, international developments the Russia-Ukraine war, the West-East conflict, the growing economic ties between China and Central Asia make the need for Turkic states to increase coordination among themselves even more urgent. The increased activity of leading Central Asian countries such as Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan within the framework of the TDT is also an indication of the ongoing nature of this process. [9]

Taking all these factors into account, the scientific study of integration processes among Turkic states, the analysis of successes and difficulties in this field, and the assessment of future prospects act as a highly relevant and strategically important research direction.

The purpose of the article. By analyzing the integration processes of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), it aims to examine the challenges faced by the organization on a regional and global scale and its future development prospects. To achieve this goal, detailed discussions will be held on the activities of the TDT in the economic, political, cultural and security fields and the problems existing in these fields. The article will also examine the existing opportunities for integration among the Turkic states and how these opportunities can be realized.

The objectives of the article are defined as follows: To examine the historical foundations of the integration processes of the Organization of Turkic States. This task will cover the reasons for the emergence of the TTS, the stages of development, and the factors affecting the integration processes. To analyze the economic, political and cultural relations between the member countries of the Organization of Turkic Speaking States. The main goal here is to understand the level of cooperation between the member countries and how this cooperation affects the development of the organization. Identifying the challenges and constraints in the integration process. This task will examine the political, economic, and cultural differences faced by the organization and their impact on integration.

To analyze the future development prospects of the Organization of Turkic States. This will include identifying the steps the organization will take to deepen integration in the future and potential areas for development. Assess the regional and global impacts of integration in the Turkic world. This task will analyze the position of the TDT in world politics and international relations and provide predictions on how the organization can increase its broader regional and global influence.

Subject and Significance of the Study.

The subject of the study is to examine the dynamics of the integration processes of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) and the effects of these processes in various fields. The study examines the level of cooperation between the TEU member states in the economic, political, security and cultural fields, the difficulties encountered in the integration processes and possible solutions to overcome these difficulties. Thus, the subject of the study covers the current state of integration among the Turkic states and the prospects for the future development of this process, as well as the role of the Organization of Turkic States at the regional and global levels and the impact of integration processes on international relations. A broader analysis is being conducted, taking into account the integration process, as well as the relations between the member states regarding their domestic policies, economic development and security cooperation.

The importance of the study emerges in several key areas:

Strengthening regional cooperation. It analyzes the future development of the Organization of Turkic States and its impact on regional stability. Strengthening ties within the Turkic world could help establish closer economic and political relations between these states.

The position of the Turkic world in global politics. It offers a perspective that will allow the Turkic states to be more active and influential in global politics. Against the backdrop of evolving global power balances and geopolitical changes, the role and prospects of the Organization of Turkic States are particularly important.

Overcoming difficulties in the integration process.

It aims to overcome obstacles to integration processes among Turkic states and to develop more effective mechanisms for cooperation between these states. Understanding the internal and external factors affecting the development of the organization can help develop more effective strategic approaches.

Strengthening cooperation in the field of culture and education.

It also emphasizes the development of cultural relations and cooperation in the field of education among the Turkic world. This is important in terms of the preservation and dissemination of the Turkish language and culture.

Recommendations for future prospects: It puts forward practical recommendations for the future development of the TDT. These recommendations are important for strengthening the integration of the organization and ensuring political and economic stability of member countries

Historical foundations of integration among Turkic states.

The historical roots of integration among Turkic states are based on common ethnicity, linguistic unity, cultural values, and ancient statehood traditions. Turkic peoples have established states, created trade routes, and formed a common culture over millennia in a vast geography stretching from Central Asia to Anatolia.

The great Turkic empires such as the Hun, Goyturk, Uyghur, Seljuk and Ottoman empires demonstrate that the joint political and cultural life of these peoples was historically possible and real [16]. In particular, the Goyturk Khaganate (6th-8th centuries) proved for the first time the possibility of unified political structures among the Turkic peoples, and the system of governance based on the principle of "El (state) and Tora (law)" laid the foundation of Turkish political culture (Sinor, 1990). During this period, the Orkhon-Yenisei monuments are considered a clear example of linguistic and cultural unity among the Turkic peoples. In later periods, through the Seljuk and Ottoman empires, the Turkic-Muslim culture was enriched and a single civilizational space was formed [15].

Although the idea of pan-Turkism and the search for political unity among the Turkic peoples intensified at the beginning of the 20th century, this idea could not be realized against the backdrop of inter-imperial competition and Soviet expansion. During the Soviet era, the Turkic republics of Central Asia were subjected to centralized administration and Russification policies for many years, but despite this, a common language, culture, and spiritual values were preserved [9]. Starting from the first summit held in Ankara in 1992, coordination efforts among Turkic-speaking states increased further, laying the foundation for institutionally based cooperation formats in the following years. Thus, historical experience and elements of common identity language, religion, culture and statehood heritage constitute the ideological and cultural foundations of the modern integration processes of Turkic-speaking states. This history is not only a memory of the past, but also a solid foundation for future cooperation.

Shared Ethnic and Cultural Bonds.

The integration processes among the Turkic States are based on great importance, especially ethnic and cultural ties. These ties play an important role in strengthening mutual relations between the member states and in the development of the organization. Common ethnic and cultural roots are one of the main factors shaping the historical and social structure of the Turkic world. These factors also have a profound impact on the social and cultural aspects of regional integration. They ensure the development of a common identity and consciousness among the Turkic States. The Turkic peoples have historically been connected to each other by many similar languages, cultures, and traditions. Ethnic affinity allows for stronger political and economic ties between states. Establishing such ethnic solidarity creates conditions for achieving positive results by taking into account the common interests of these peoples [10]. The Turkish language, literature, music and culture in general act as one of the unifying factors between states. These cultural ties allow for a stronger connection, especially among the younger generation, and serve to strengthen the unity of the Turkic world [7]. One of the foundations of the success of the integration of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is precisely the strengthening of these cultural and ethnic ties. Taking these common ties into account, the OTS seeks to increase cooperation between member countries in education, tourism, sports and other areas. Strengthening cultural exchange and relations also facilitates social integration between these states. For example, the teaching of Turkish language and literature creates conditions for mutual understanding of different cultures and the formation of close cooperation between these states [11]. Strengthening ethnic and cultural unity among the Turkic world will lead to many positive political and economic results not only at the regional but also at the international level. This will help to increase the collective influence of the Turkic states and take a stronger position in the world.

Post Soviet Regional Dynamics

The collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991 led to the emergence of new geopolitical dynamics not only in the Central Asian and Caucasus regions, but also among the Turkic states. This event created an opportunity for the countries of the region to emerge as independent states and determine their positions in the system of international relations. Also, this was the beginning of a new era of integration processes among the Turkic states. It led to the formation of new integration trends in the

Turkic world based on various natural and human factors. Having regained their independence, the Turkic states began to look for various ways for cooperation in both political and economic fields. During the Soviet period, many Turkic-speaking peoples were limited to different cultures and languages, but after independence, these countries began to regain their ethnic and cultural identities [10]. During this period, the establishment of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) laid the foundation for the development of independent but close relations between these countries. At the same time, this regional organization, for the first time since independence, began to take important steps to expand the political and cultural ties of the Turkic states. The establishment of the TDT created the basis for these states to pursue an independent foreign policy and unite for the sake of common interests [7]. The Turkic states, endowed with natural resources and strategic locations, have realized that economic integration in the region will be an important factor by accelerating their economic development. At the same time, increasing economic interdependence between these countries has played an important role in ensuring regional stability. These integration processes have created conditions for greater regional economic independence and reduced dependence on Western countries [11]. The global and regional security environment has necessitated closer cooperation among independent states. Cooperation in this area has also allowed these states to take more independent positions vis-à-vis Russia and other foreign powers. Cooperation between Turkic states, especially in the security and military fields, has taken a more significant place in the post-Soviet regional dynamics [12]. The regional changes and integration process that took place in the Turkic world after the collapse of the Soviet Union also encouraged the formation of a new cultural community based on cultural and linguistic ties. The preservation and promotion of the Turkish language and culture has contributed to the development of intercultural relations in the region, to better understanding of people and to the implementation of joint cultural projects. This regional dynamic has ensured that the Turkic states have gained greater global recognition and strengthened their positions after independence.

First Cooperation Initiatives in the 1990s. The 1990s were a period of independent policies for Turkic-speaking states after the collapse of the Soviet Union. During this period, cooperation, especially within the Turkic world, began to take shape, laying the foundation for a new geopolitical environment and regional integration in the region. The first initiatives of cooperation among the Turkic states that gained independence manifested themselves in both political, economic and cultural fields. In connection with the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Turkic states gained their independence in the first half of 1991. The most important initiative of this period was the establishment of the Council of Heads of State of the Turkic States in 1992. This council was established to develop political, economic and cultural cooperation between Turkic-speaking states and laid the foundation for a new model of cooperation for the Turkic world. At the first meeting, many economic and political issues were discussed within the Council and the basic principles for cooperation were defined [7]. Towards the end of the 1990s, the establishment of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) in 2009 showed that these cooperation initiatives had become a formal and institutional form. The establishment of this organization has created an opportunity to further strengthen relations and integration among the Turkic states. This initiative also aimed to develop common interests in the political, economic and cultural fields among the member states. One of the most important results is that the Turkic states have demonstrated solidarity and unity in pursuing independent policies [10]. In the 1990s, cooperation initiatives also emerged in the economic sphere. Initiatives such as the Trans-Caspian Trade and Communication Program, which included Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan, aimed at developing economic relations between the Turkic states. Such initiatives aimed to strengthen trade relations, facilitate border crossings, and ensure regional economic development. Economic ties were also further strengthened through organizations such as the Turkish Eximbank and the Turkish Exporters' Union [11]. The promotion of cultural relations among the Turkic world was also among the initial cooperation initiatives in the 1990s. In 1992, joint activities in the field of culture were initiated within the framework of the Turkic Language Confederation. This initiative supported the teaching of the Turkish language and literature and aimed at preserving

Turkish culture and traditions. In addition, the Turkish Culture and Arts Foundation was established for the purpose of cooperation in the field of education among the Turkic world [12].

In the 1990s, the cooperation initiatives of the Turkic states in the political field also increased. The Turkic states that gained independence developed their diplomatic relations in order to maintain stability in the region and defend their common interests. Also, joint political efforts were made to ensure stability in the Caucasus and Central Asia. This cooperation also allowed the unification and strengthening of the positions of the Turkic states in international organizations [7]

Political cooperation between the Turkic States has been developing since the 1990s as a fundamental way to protect the independence of these states and defend their common interests. The development of political relations, especially after the restoration of independence of the Turkic states, has created conditions for the formation of more effective diplomatic and political positions both at the regional and international levels. Since the Turkic world is closely connected by its common ethnic and cultural identities, history and traditions, these relations have created a positive basis for mutual understanding and cooperation.

The basic principles of political cooperation began to develop, first in the form of bilateral and trilateral relations, and then on a wider scale through regional organizations and institutions. This cooperation also created an opportunity for the Turkic states to represent their joint positions on the international stage. The Council of Turkic Heads of State, established in 1992, has been an institution that constitutes the main framework for political cooperation between the Turkic states.

This council was established to pursue a joint policy among member states and defend common interests [7]. The political cooperation of the Turkic states was accompanied by taking common positions, especially in regional and international organizations. In the 1990s, these states, which gained their independence, determined common positions for joint participation in a number of international organizations.

With the establishment of the Organization of Turkic States, these states began to approach political issues in a more systematic and coordinated manner. The TDT has enabled member states to take common positions on joint political and diplomatic issues. For example, within the framework of this organization, Turkic states have supported each other on various global issues, especially in the areas of terrorism, security and regional stability. Also, common interests were promoted in the Turkic world in order to strengthen political partnership and more effectively represent each state independently at the international level [11].

Security and Political Stability. After gaining their independence, the Turkic states also began to act jointly on security issues. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, new security threats emerged in the region. The common position of the Turkic states in combating these threats led to their mutual support for each other and the development of common security strategies. For example, security issues have been discussed within the framework of the Turkic Council and other political organizations, and joint action plans have been prepared to protect the security interests of Turkic states [10].

Democratic Values and Human Rights. Another important aspect of political cooperation is the development of common positions on democratic values and human rights issues. Turkic states have promoted common values in the areas of democracy, human rights and the protection of rights. By working together on these issues, Turkic states have not only developed their own political systems, but also sought to respect and spread democratic principles worldwide. Member states have applied these principles to their domestic policies and have also demonstrated common positions in this area in international relations [12].

Beginning of Economic Cooperation and Trade Relations. Economic cooperation among Turkic states first began to develop in the early 1990s with policies and initiatives defined within the framework of the Council of Heads of State of Turkic States. Within this framework, many agreements have been signed to enhance cooperation in key economic sectors, increase trade exchange, and deepen economic integration. These agreements have facilitated the establishment of

a free trade zone among Turkic states and the expansion of economic cooperation on a mutually beneficial basis [11].

Transport Corridors and Cooperation. Strengthening transport infrastructure and creating corridors has been an important issue for the development of economic relations between Turkic states. A number of international transport corridors and infrastructure projects have been implemented to support the development of trade relations between these states and increase regional integration. The Trans-Caspian Corridor is one of the most important initiatives in this regard. It has facilitated increased trade relations between Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan and Turkey and provided more efficient transport routes between the countries bordering the Caspian Sea. The Baku-Tbilisi-Kars Railway is also an important part of this cooperation and aims to create a faster and safer transport connection between Asia and Europe. Also, through these corridors, Turkish states have increased their exports to Europe and other regions [7].

Another important project, the North-South Corridor, covers the transit routes of Russia, Iran, and Azerbaijan. This project has increased transportation opportunities between the Turkic states, accelerating trade and creating strategic regional ties [12].

Economic Development and Regional Inter-Power Cooperation. The economic relations of the Turkic states are not only related to trade and transport, but also to the regulation of inter-power relations in the region and the establishment of alliances. Deepening the economic partnership between these states will ensure their stronger position in the world economy. Strengthening regional economic integration in the Turkic world will ensure cooperation in broader economic areas and the greater influence of these states in the international arena [10].

Education, Culture and Information Exchange. An important aspect of integration among Turkic states is related to the strengthening of education, culture and information exchange. These three areas play an important role in strengthening cultural ties between states and preserving common values. Also, cooperation in the field of education and cultural exchange is one of the main tools supporting social and integration processes in the Turkic world. This exchange increases cooperation between different nations through mutual understanding and joint projects.

Cooperation in the Field of Education and Joint Programs. Cooperation in the field of education among Turkic states first began in the 1990s within the framework of the Council of Heads of State of Turkic States and the Turkic Council. This cooperation aimed to support the development of the education system of each state and to strengthen regional education programs. For example, the Turkish Academic Network (TÜRKA) operates to strengthen academic exchange between universities in member states. Within the framework of this network, student exchange programs, joint educational projects and scientific research have been promoted. Also, joint programs and courses on Turkish Language and Culture have been organized, which has increased opportunities for joint language and cultural teaching among the Turkic world [11].

Joint education programs of Turkic states promote the exchange of experience in the modernization of their education systems and the application of modern educational methods. These programs also help member states train highly qualified specialists [10].

Cultural Cooperation and Shared Values. Cultural cooperation among Turkic states is based on common historical, ethnic and religious ties. This cooperation also creates conditions for different cultures to come closer to each other and deepen mutual understanding. Through cultural exchange events, festivals, exhibitions and conferences, each state introduces its cultural heritage to other countries. For example, joint events on Turkish Culture and Heritage form the basis of cultural cooperation and mutual respect between these states [7]. Turkic states have implemented a number of projects to protect cultural heritage and traditions. These projects are of great importance, especially in the areas of spreading culture, preserving historical monuments, and preserving traditions. They also serve socio-political stability in the Turkic world as a means of supporting cultural exchange, education, and trade relations [12].

Information Exchange and Media Cooperation. Information exchange, media cooperation and coordination in journalism among Turkic states ensure that these states are represented in a stronger

and more organized manner in the international arena. For this purpose, institutions such as the Turkic States Press Union and the Turkish Journalists Union have been established. These institutions strengthen the exchange of experience in journalism among Turkic states, implement joint media projects, and introduce the culture, politics, and economy of each state to other states [7].

The development of information technologies and the increase in information exchange in the Turkic world further deepen the integration between these states. The Turkish Language Information Platform (TÜRKIP) and other web-based projects support joint activities among member states and increase the speed of information exchange. Through these platforms, innovations in the cultural and educational fields in the Turkic states are shared more quickly and delivered to a wider audience [10].

Defense and Security Cooperation. An important aspect of integration among Turkic-speaking states is defense and security cooperation. This cooperation aims to ensure regional stability, prevent conflicts, and address common security issues. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, these states began to cooperate together to pursue their own independent foreign policies and solve regional security problems. Turkic states have implemented various joint measures to strengthen cooperation in the field of defense, ensure regional security and prevent external threats. One of the most important initiatives in this context is the establishment of the Turkish Defense Cooperation Agency in 1992.

It took place within the framework of the Turkic Council. The Council has further developed cooperation on security issues and has sought to formulate a common defense policy of its member states [7]. Joint military exercises and security discussions have been held between the member states of the Turkic Council, and technical support and military experience exchange has been carried out in order to increase the defense capabilities of each state. This cooperation has also expanded to the areas of border security, anti-terrorism, arms control, and the fight against drugs [10].

Joint Defense Organizations and Cooperation Among Turkic States. Several relevant organizations have been established among Turkic states to address joint defense and security issues. These organizations play an important role in avoiding military conflicts between states and resolving mutual security issues. For example, the Turkish War Academy and the Turkic World Defense Policy Forum are important initiatives in this area. Military exercises and mutual expert exchanges have been organized to strengthen cooperation between Turkic states. These events allow states to cooperate more closely on regional security issues [12].

Military Technologies and Defense Industry. Cooperation in the field of defense industry among Turkic states has also expanded. This cooperation has allowed each state to create an independent defense industry and implement new military technologies. The states have implemented joint projects in the fields of joint technology development, arms production and military equipment. Such cooperation not only accelerates security but also accelerates economic development in the region and increases the international military power of the Turkic world [10].

Geopolitical Obstacles and External Influences. The integration process of the Turkic states is affected by a number of geopolitical obstacles and external influences. These obstacles are related to the complexity of the regional and global political environment and can complicate the joint activities of these states. The influence of developed and developing powers on these states, as well as factors affecting domestic and foreign policy, are among the main factors preventing the Turkish states from achieving their integration goals. The biggest geopolitical obstacle to integration among the Turkic states is the long-term security and conflict issues in the region. In particular, the instability in the South Caucasus and Central Asia makes it difficult for these states to implement a joint regional policy. The Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict, Russia's military intervention in Georgia, and other conflicts are among the factors limiting the regional cooperation activities of the Turkic states [11]. Also, the influence of major powers such as Russia, China and the United States, which are unofficial power centers in these regions, complicates the political and economic integration of the Turkic world. These states, in order to protect their geopolitical interests, try to weaken the relations between the Turkic states by interfering in various ways [12]. Another factor that weakens the integration of the Turkic states is the strategic influence of foreign states on these countries. In particular, Russia and China are using various political and economic tools to establish hegemony in the Turkic world.

Russia's peacekeeping operations in Central Asia and the Caucasus also demonstrate its desire to control these states' energy resources. Such external influences may conflict with the national interests of the Turkic states and hinder their integration goals [10]. China is also trying to increase its economic influence in Central Asia and the South Caucasus through the "One Belt, One Road" project. Although this project can develop economic relations between Turkic states, it also creates conditions for the implementation of China's dominance policy. China's position in this region is also one of the factors that complicates political cooperation between states [12].

Western Influence. Another external influence on the integration of the Turkic states is the influence of Western countries - especially the European Union and the United States. The European Union and the United States attach special importance to strategic cooperation with these states, but sometimes this cooperation is limited in relation to the political and economic goals of the West. It is possible that the West, in order to secure its own interests, may influence joint policies and integration initiatives among the Turkic states. Such external influences complicate the efforts of Turkic states to strengthen their regional unity and sometimes prevent the formation of mutual trust [11]. Many Turkic states pursue a multi-vector foreign policy, that is, they seek to establish positive relations with the West, Russia, and China.

Political and Economic Differences Between Member States. One of the main challenges facing the integration process among the Turkic states is the political and economic differences that exist among the member states. These differences are related to the foreign policies of the states, levels of economic development, social structures and forms of governance. The impact of these differences on the integration process creates various obstacles in both political relations and economic cooperation. There are significant differences in political structure among the Turkic states. Each state's political system has its own unique governance structure that has been shaped historically. For example, Turkey has a strong centralized political structure, combining a long-standing parliamentarism and a presidential system. This determines its position in international relations and its approach to regional security issues. On the other hand, in countries such as Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, presidential power is still dominant, but there are more attempts at political reforms and democracy in these countries [10]. Political differences also affect the foreign policy approaches of the Turkic states. For example, Azerbaijan builds its independent and sometimes ambiguous foreign policy in accordance with both regional security issues and its own national interests. Turkey, on the other hand, aims to strengthen its ties with Europe by becoming a member of NATO. Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, on the other hand, pursue a more neutral foreign policy and try to stay away from regional conflicts. These political differences make it difficult for the Turkic states to formulate a joint foreign policy and slow down the integration process [7]. There are also significant differences in the level of economic development and structure among the Turkic states. Turkey is the most economically powerful state in the region. Its economy is characterized by a largely developed industrial sector, rich natural resources, and strong infrastructure. This ensures Turkey's economic leadership in the region and allows it to continue its economic assistance to other Turkic states [11]. Among other Turkic states, countries such as Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan are known for their rich natural resources, but are still developing in the industrial and agricultural sectors. Kyrgyzstan and Turkmenistan have built their economies more on natural resources and agricultural products, but their economies still do not have a strong industrial base [12]. Economic differences also affect trade relations between states. Turkey, with its strong industrial base and developed trade relations, is a major trading partner among these countries. In addition, countries such as Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, which are rich in energy resources, have more liberal economic policies in the areas of trade and investment [10]. Economic differences between Turkic states also complicate the development of regional trade relations. Some states, advocating an increased role of the state in the economy, advocate more state intervention in their economic policies. On the other hand, states with less developed economies want a market economy and attract more foreign investment. This situation complicates the coordination of trade relations among Turkic states and creates obstacles to the formation of joint trade areas [11].

The differences between the more developed states (Turkey, Kazakhstan) and the developing ones (Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan) among the Turkic states create economic and political pressures on the integration process. The different levels of social and economic development among these states, as well as issues of political trust, may hinder the success of joint cooperation and integration initiatives. However, these differences, in turn, can create conditions for strengthening cooperation between Turkic-speaking states in various fields and developing complementary economies [7].

One of the main factors complicating the integration process among Turkic states is organizational and legal differences. These differences arise from the fact that each state has its own independent legal and organizational systems and limit joint activities and integration. States play a key role in both regional cooperation structures, both administratively and institutionally, as well as in general policy. The differences in organizational structures and institutions involved in the process among Turkic states are the basis for identifying these state structures that complicate the process. States play a key role in both regional cooperation structures, both administratively and institutionally, as well as in general policy. The differences in organizational structures and institutions involved in the process among Turkic states are the basis for identifying these state structures that complicate the process. For example, Turkey is implementing its development risk in relation to the European Union and NATO and is establishing relations with these organizations. On the other hand, states such as Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan are trying to maintain more independence organizationally and are used to joining structures [10].

Turkic states mainly cooperate within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), but there are different levels and different goals within the structure of this organization. The OTS aims to develop political, economic and cultural relations between different states, but the work of this organization still has very different organizational models. For example, Turkey is the most active member of this organization and puts forward numerous diplomatic initiatives, but other countries, such as Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, sometimes welcome these initiatives with caution and are still defining the goals and functions of the organization [7].

For example, Turkey is the most active member of this organization and puts forward numerous diplomatic initiatives, but other countries, such as Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, sometimes welcome these initiatives with caution and are still defining the goals and functions of the organization [7]. From a legal perspective, there are a number of differences in the integration process among the Turkic states. Each state's independent legal system and approach to international law determine its relations with organizations and integration activities. For example, while Turkey is carrying out legal harmonization processes to become a member of the European Union, countries such as Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan are more inclined to preserve their independence and domestic legislation. This creates obstacles in the process of approximation of legal structures and principles [11].

Another important difference between the legal systems of the Turkish states arises in the approach to international treaties and legal documents. Turkey has implemented numerous legislative reforms in line with international law and European standards, and is trying to integrate international legal principles into its domestic law. On the contrary, some states, such as Turkmenistan, prefer to preserve their independent legal and political traditions and try to stay away from international influences [10]. The legal framework of the organizations of which the Turkic-speaking states are members also varies. Within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), the organization's activities are based more on cooperation and mutual understanding. However, the legal framework of this organization is still developing, and the issue of unification of legal norms among the member states has not yet been fully resolved.

The definition and harmonization of legal norms within the framework of the TEU is one of the main obstacles to political and economic integration among member states [12]. On the other hand, the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), while requiring any legal convergence among Turkic-speaking states, is somewhat more difficult to implement. Some states do not accept the full legal system of this organization and prefer to protect their national rights [7].

One of the important aspects of integration among Turkic states is ensuring regional stability and energy security. These states, with their strategic positions and rich energy resources, play an important role in regional and global energy supply. Countries such as Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan are important regional players in energy supply with their oil and gas fields, which strengthens their role in regional stability.

Energy security issues among Turkic states are not only related to economic cooperation but also to regional security. These states are trying to ensure regional stability through energy routes and infrastructure projects. Projects such as the Trans Adriatic Pipeline (TAP) and Shah Deniz, in addition to increasing energy security, also strengthen regional integration. However, regional security issues and external interference are among the factors affecting this cooperation [11].

Joint Activities of Turkic States at the International Level

Turkic states work together at the international level, mainly within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) and other regional platforms. This cooperation aims to strengthen mutual support in the political, economic and cultural spheres. Turkic states, in general, strive to support each other in international affairs and protect their common interests.

In particular, close cooperation between Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Turkey in the economic and energy fields increases their international influence. In addition, Turkic states are trying to increase their influence at the global level by promoting the spread of Turkish culture and language in the world [7]. Turkic states accept digital transformation as a key factor in economic development and integration processes.

The development of information and communication technologies (ICT) plays an important role in further strengthening the joint economy of these countries and in faster integration. The development of the digital economy creates new investment opportunities and areas of cooperation, especially for countries such as Turkey, Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan. In the future, initiatives are expected to increase digital connectivity and technological cooperation between these countries.

The expansion of trade and economic relations between Turkic states through digital platforms will boost the development of innovative areas such as e-commerce and blockchain technologies. At the same time, joint projects and initiatives in the field of cybersecurity and digital infrastructure are expected between these states, which will serve to increase regional stability and integration [12].

Turkish Communities Outside the Borders of Turkish States and Their Role

The process of integration among Turkic-speaking states is not limited to the mutual cooperation of sovereign states. This process is also expanding through the activities of non-independent public associations and cultural organizations belonging to Turkic-speaking peoples. Tatars, Bashkirs, Uyghurs, Chuvashs, Sakhas, Kazakhs and Turkmen living in the Russian Federation, China, Iran, Afghanistan and other multinational countries have organized themselves into various organizations in order to preserve and develop the Turkic cultural identity.

Among such associations, the World Uyghur Congress (Germany), Tatar National Cultural Autonomies, Bashkir People's Congress, Chuvash National Congress, Sakha Cultural Societies, South Azerbaijan National Awakening Movement (GAMOH) and Turkmen diaspora associations occupy a special place. The mentioned organizations operate at the regional and international levels in the direction of protecting the Turkic identity, promoting national-cultural values and protecting rights. At the same time, they play a mediator role in establishing cultural relations with Turkic states and contribute to the formation of diaspora diplomacy.

The activities of these associations are of strategic importance for the mutual solidarity of the Turkic states. As such, through these organizations, the Turkic states can establish relations with their compatriots outside their borders on cultural, humanitarian, and sometimes political platforms. This creates conditions for the expansion of both the geographical and spiritual borders of the Turkic world [12].

Integration areas and areas of cooperation. The development of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is not limited to political and economic cooperation; the organization also aims to expand cooperation in the fields of education, culture, transportation, security and tourism. These

areas of cooperation are part of the various strategies implemented by the organization for regional solidarity, peace and development.

Problems and limitations in the integration process.

The problems and limitations in the integration process of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) create certain difficulties in terms of both the formation of regional solidarity and the development of interstate relations. These problems are mainly manifested in the political, economic, cultural and security areas.

Political differences and national interests remain the biggest obstacle to the development of the TDC. The differences in the national interests and domestic policies of each member state complicate collective decision-making. For example, the priority given to relations with Russia by Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan in some cases prevents the organization from formulating a unified policy [7]. At the same time, competition for regional leadership among different member states also stands in the way of integration.

Economic dependence and uneven levels of development Another important problem area is the economic dependence and uneven levels of development among the TDC countries. The economic structures and resource potentials of the countries are different, which makes it difficult to adopt common economic policies. For example, the level of economic development of Azerbaijan and Turkey is higher than that of other member countries. These differences can create obstacles to the expansion of economic cooperation [1].

Language and cultural differences Language and culture, which are one of the unifying elements in the Turkic world, can sometimes also cause separation. Although there is a common language of communication among Turkic languages, each country's own cultural and linguistic differences create difficulties in implementing the joint cultural programs of the TDC. For example, certain differences between the Uzbek and Kazakh languages, as well as Azerbaijani and Turkish, can affect the effectiveness of cultural projects and events [12].

Political instability and security issues The ongoing internal and regional security problems in most TEU member states also complicate the integration process of the organization. In particular, regional conflicts, such as the Karabakh conflict, strain relations between member states and hinder the definition of joint security policies. Security concerns related to Azerbaijan's conflict experience also affect other countries, making it difficult to find common ground on collective security issues [11].

The influence of the geopolitical environment The geopolitical environment also has a significant impact on the integration process of the TDC. The interests of major powers such as Russia and China limit the organization's space for action. Russia perceives the unification of the Turkic world as a threat to its position and therefore tries to influence the foreign policy of each of the Turkic states in the region. The TDC's increasing influence as a regional power center may not be positively perceived by other world powers [10].

Nevertheless, the member states of the Turkic States Organization are conducting intensive discussions to overcome these problems and are trying to implement relevant reforms. As a result, the TSO, despite the difficulties it faces, is making significant progress in the integration process.

Future Development Prospects of the Turkic States Organization

The future development prospects of the Turkic States Organization aim to ensure deeper integration and solidarity among the member states of the organization. These prospects are based on both political and economic changes in the region and events taking place on a global scale. The future development of the Turkic States Organization can be considered mainly in three main directions: economic integration, security cooperation and the development of cultural relations. Strengthening economic integration is one of the main goals of the development of the TDC. Deepening economic cooperation between member countries, increasing regional trade and investment flows, creating a common market and implementing economic projects are the basis for the organization's future success. In this regard,

Strengthening cooperation in the field of security will also play an important role in the future of the Turkic States Organization. The development of military and security cooperation between the Turkic states serves the purpose of maintaining regional stability and combating new security threats that occur regularly. In this direction, it is important to create joint platforms for discussing security issues among the organization's member states, to take joint measures in the areas of cybersecurity, border security, and the fight against terrorism. At the same time, strengthening the defense position against pressure from foreign powers such as Russia and China is also one of the future development prospects of the TDT [12].

Regional and global balance of power The development prospects of the TEU are not limited to deepening cooperation between member states. The future development of the organization is also related to the global balance of power. Member states, by pursuing a joint policy, can position themselves as a stronger party in international relations. The geopolitical changes taking place on a global scale and new cooperation opportunities create important conditions for the Turkic States Organization to increase its role. In this regard, the organization is expected to cooperate more actively with international organizations, especially the UN, SCO and other regional organizations [10]. In the future, steps taken towards strengthening the Organization of Turkic States and deeper integration will further strengthen the unity of the Turkic world and increase the influence of this organization on a regional and global scale.

Conclusion

The Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is an organization that brings together countries with diverse historical, cultural and political backgrounds and has made significant progress towards regional integration. Despite some difficulties experienced in the integration process, cooperation in the economic, cultural and security fields among the TTS member states has great potential to ensure regional stability and comprehensive development. The main directions of the development of the Turkic States Organization are increasing economic cooperation between member countries, strengthening joint activities on security issues and strengthening ties in the field of culture. Steps taken in these directions will ensure that the TSO operates more efficiently and in a coordinated manner. Projects such as the Zangezur Corridor and the Trans-Caspian Transport March continue to create great opportunities to stimulate the economic development of the organization and mutual trade between member countries. In the field of security, the member states of the TEU should strive to form a stronger defense structure and a common security policy, taking into account global and regional threats. This will also help maintain regional stability against pressures from powers such as Russia and China. In addition, the cooperation of the TEU in the field of culture and language is of great importance in terms of preserving and strengthening the common heritage of the Turkic world.

The organization's promotion of intercultural dialogue will allow for closer ties between the Turkic world and increase the influence of Turkish culture in the world. The realization of all these potentials will enable the TDT to become not only a regional organization, but also an institution that increases its importance on the global stage. In the future, the integration processes of the Organization of Turkic States will deepen further, strengthen the unity of the Turkic world and have a wider impact on the world scale.

Summary of the Results Achieved

The integration process among the Turkic states has shown progress in many political, economic and cultural areas. Joint cooperation and integration initiatives within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) have strengthened regional cooperation among these states. At the same time, the development of economic relations between the states has created new opportunities, especially in the fields of energy and trade. At the same time, legal and organizational differences in the structure of the organization, various geopolitical obstacles and economic and political differences between the member states have been factors slowing down the pace of integration.

At the same time, due to the independent legal and political approaches of each state, some difficulties have arisen in implementing joint activities. The results obtained show that the integration

of Turkic states will be strengthened not only through regional cooperation, but also through cooperation in areas such as global energy security and digital transformation. In the future, even closer cooperation and the development of the integration process between these states will be of great importance for regional stability and economic growth.

Recommendations for Deepening Integration in the Future

A number of recommendations can be put forward for further deepening integration among Turkic states in the future.

1. Legal and Organizational Harmonization. Identification and harmonization of the legal and organizational structure among the Turkic states should be ensured. Harmonizing the independent legal system of each state in the integration process will facilitate inter-organizational cooperation and prevent legal difficulties. This will further strengthen the legal framework within the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) and ensure that joint activities among member states are more systematic and effective.

2. Strengthening Economic and Trade Cooperation. Cooperation in the energy and transport sectors is one of the key factors for deepening economic integration among the Turkic-speaking states. Economic ties, simplification of trade tariffs, establishment of free trade zones and joint development of economic infrastructure projects will contribute to further expansion of economic ties between these states and ensuring economic stability.

3. Digital Transformation and Technological Cooperation. The development of the digital economy will create new areas of cooperation between the Turkic states. Joint initiatives in the fields of technological innovations, e-commerce and cybersecurity will accelerate the development of digital relations between the states. This will also create conditions for a more integrated regional market and the expansion of trade relations on a digital basis.

4. Political and Diplomatic Integration. In order to deepen political cooperation, Turkic states should define common positions and ensure the adoption of common policies and decisions at the international level. Joint activities in international organizations will increase the political influence of these states and allow them to defend common interests more effectively.

5. Increasing Cooperation in the Field of Culture and Education. Cooperation in the fields of culture and education will not only create rapprochement and mutual understanding between the peoples of the Turkic states, but will also strengthen the social foundations of the integration process. Cultural exchange programs, joint universities and educational networks should be established, which will serve the development of human capital and the strengthening of social ties between the countries.

6. Coordination in the Field of International Stability and Security. Turkic states should cooperate together to ensure regional stability and security. Cooperation in security issues, especially in matters such as cybersecurity, the fight against terrorism and the resolution of regional conflicts, should be increased. Military cooperation and the establishment of joint defense structures among these states will also strengthen integration in the field of security.

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